

«COMPARATIVE ASPECTS OF LONG AND SHORT SHAFTS, IN ORDER TO
JUSTIFY THE FEASIBILITY OF THEIR REPLACEMENT»

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*"Vergleichende Aspekte von langen und kurzen Wellen
um die Machbarkeit ihres Austauschs zu begründen"*

Annotation: *Shafts are classified according to their purpose, according to the shape of the axis, according to the shape of the section. In this article, a comparative analysis of two shafts having different lengths, their scope was carried out, and all the advantages and disadvantages of both long and short shafts were studied.*

Keywords: *Shaft, long shaft, short shaft, rod, bending stiffness, strength.*

Anmerkung: *Wellen werden nach ihrem Zweck klassifiziert, nach der Form der Achse, nach der Form des Abschnitts. In diesem Artikel wurde eine vergleichende Analyse von zwei Wellen mit unterschiedlichen Längen und deren Umfang durchgeführt, und es wurden alle Vor- und Nachteile von langen und kurzen Wellen untersucht.*

Schlüsselwörter: *Welle, lange Welle, kurze Welle, Stab, Biegesteifigkeit, Festigkeit.*

Shaft parts of various types and lengths are widely used in any engineering products. They are the leading elements of machines for various purposes and technical systems.

The manufacturing process of the shafts is not complicated, since they do not have a complex design. However, it is known that parts such as large round rods

($L \gg D$) are difficult to process, although they generally do not have hard-to-reach areas for processing. This is due to the insufficient rigidity of the rod, because of this, significant deformations can occur during processing. There are also serious problems that arise when fixing work pieces during their installation on the machine.

Shafts longer than 1.5 m can be classified as long shafts. Those of them that have a length to diameter ratio of more than 10 can be classified as non-rigid. Unfortunately, we know that with an increase in the length of the shaft, its strength decreases, and they are called long shafts.

The operability of the structure as a whole depends on their strength and reliability, and from this it follows that during operation, parts of the shaft type must comply not only with the conditions of strength, but also with rigidity.

Many designers and technologists pay more attention to low-rigid shafts, which serve to transmit torques over sufficiently long distances, of course, within the design, which is their main advantage over short shafts. Reducing the material consumption of these parts is carried out mainly due to a decrease in the cross section. Long shafts are used mainly in transport and textile machinery, in metal-cutting machines.

A long rod has low stability and low bending stiffness, which leads to serious consequences during their processing and assembly, so such parts are usually low-tech.

Often, under the action of forces during rotation, long shafts can bend even from their own weight. However, all representatives of mechanical engineering are well aware that the process of increasing the flexural rigidity of parts such as a shaft is very difficult.

In the disconnecter mechanisms, torsionally short shafts should also be used, if possible. The advantages of such parts include, first of all, their strength index. The use of short shafts is more technologically advanced than the use of long shafts.

Findings:

In this analysis of the literature, comparing long and short shafts, their advantages and disadvantages were highlighted, which have both scientific and experimental justification.

Comparison of long and short shafts turned out to be inappropriate, since the essence and purpose of their use is different. It is advisable to eliminate the shortcomings of these shafts, namely, to find the optimal solution for increasing the flexural rigidity and increasing the strength of the shafts.

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